

Citation Analysis of Master’s Dissertations Submitted to the Department of Sociology and Anthropology, University of Maiduguri, Borno State

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Abstract

Keywords
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Introduction: This paper examined citation analysis of master’s dissertations submitted to the Department of Sociology and Anthropology, University of Maiduguri, Borno State, from 2010 to 2019.

Method: To achieve the study’s objectives, a descriptive research design using bibliometric techniques was employed. Documentary analysis served as the instrument of the study. The population comprised 67 master's dissertations submitted to the department from 2010 to 2019. Given the small and manageable size of the population, a Census Sampling Technique was adopted. The dissertations were analyzed using descriptive statistics, including frequency counts and percentages.

Results/Findings: The findings revealed that there were nine different types of materials cited, with books being the most frequently cited, followed by journals. The most frequently cited book title was "Population and Development Review," and the most frequently cited journal was the "Journal of Abnormal Child Psychology." The study also found that the majority of the citations were over 11 years old, indicating that they were not current.

Conclusion: The study concluded that books are the predominant source of citations in master’s dissertations, but many cited materials are outdated.

Recommendations: Postgraduate students should cite more journals than books due to their easy access, free availability, and currency. Additionally, the acquisitions units of the university library, in collaboration with various academic departments, should procure more books to ensure efficient and effective resource development, providing current and relevant information materials. Furthermore, postgraduate students should focus on searching for current information materials to promote and enhance new knowledge.

Introduction

Citation refers to the list of references to other works in a published work. Referring, means mentioning in the proper context and giving an explicit bibliographic statement in a list of references. That is why older articles are cited by or will receive citations from newer one (Rousseau, 2008). The citations also known as reference is therefore a branch of Bibliometric that examines the citations found in publications such as journal articles and books (Georgas and Cullars, 2005) Bibliometric generally is a set of measurement techniques which are usually used with the application of mathematical and statistical methods to books and other media of communication. Bibliometric say-to speak, is not a single term it includes informatics, scientometrics, webometrics altmetrics, and citation analysis, among others. It is conventionally used by the librarians and professionals related to the subject of library and information science for studying the process of communication, information flows, and related topics for better understanding and effective management and dissemination of information (University of Maryland (2022).

A dissertation is a document submitted in support of candidature for an academic master's degree or professional qualification presenting the authors research and findings. Dissertation is one of the requirements for the award of degree of masters in sociology and anthropology in every higher institutions of learning, especially University of Maiduguri. Usually an approved topic on any aspect of sociology and anthropology work to be researched and reported upon. A seminar is required on the approved topic prior to the completion and submission of the dissertation to the school of post-graduate studies. Mahajan & Kumar (2017) observed that citation analysis is actually a branch of information science in which researchers studied the way articles in a scholarly field are

accessed and referenced by others. It has been used for the purpose of scholarly analysis and evaluation in several fields of human endeavor. The meaning of dissertations to most students seems not to be adequately utilized. In this study, citation analysis is employed in studying 67 master's Degree dissertation submitted to the Department of Sociology and Anthropology University of Maiduguri were completed over a 10-year period (2010-2019) in order to identify the types and the trends of the citation used in the dissertations.

Statement of the Problem

The provision of information resources to students, academics researchers and other category of users lies upon its mother library it is necessary for a library to provide adequate as well as relevant information resources that will meet the needs of its users. Even with the availability of information resources in the library, postgraduate students alongside other users don't exhaust or explore the library resources adequately and properly. Library is most times considered as reading room instead of research laboratory.

Also library supposed to be a breeding ground for the harvest of greater ideas; wisdom and knowledge. Library users' now prefer using the internet to satisfy their information needs. The importance of books shelves cannot be overemphasized, through this; a library will know the materials that are heavily used and those that require consideration. All the above critical challenges are faced by the library. To this end, in order to make rational decisions on what materials should be in the shelves and what can be moved out of the shelves, it can be assessed by examining the age of cited resources by library users. It is against this backdrop and with evidence indicating that such practices are not common in Nigerian universities that this study has become imperative aimed at analyzing citations in the

Library Master's degree dissertation with a view to bridging the gap and creating the awareness for librarians in this part of the globe to understand the needs for analyzing citations in these valuable information resources using Ramat Library, University of Maiduguri, Nigeria theses submitted from 2010 to 2019 as case in point.

However, preliminary observation by the researcher revealed that not all subject areas have received equal coverage in citation analysis, to provide academic libraries with wealth of data for collection development policies. The availability of fake information resources will be too much as no bibliographic control on all information resources will be fully controlled on the internet. Citation analysis will be difficult if not impossible as well quantitative analysis may not be possible on the internet.

Citation analysis of master's dissertations is one of the methods used to measure library use by post graduate students, who are frequent clients of the library. Dissertations obviously show the desires of postgraduate students and even indicate the research specialties of the faculty and department in particular. Citation analysis is seen as a veritable tool, because citation analysis can act as a tool for selecting and de-selecting materials as it provides insight into the materials that are selected by various user groups (Onwubiko, E. chidiadi 2023). It can be a useful technique for identifying potential collection development weaknesses.

However, it has been observed that there is lack of analysis on master's dissertations submitted to the department of sociology and anthropology, University of Maiduguri. This development contravenes the idea of knowledge improvement and to the researcher is a wake up call that there is the need to update our knowledge in citation analysis on master's dissertations submitted to the

department of sociology and anthropology from 2010 to 2019 and other academic departments in order to avoid unwanted repetition of some research areas. Furthermore, there is no current data showing that Ramat library is providing citation analysis of references in theses and dissertations and there is insufficient knowledge on areas researched as to knowing areas yet to be researched so as to ensure proper citation analysis. This study which is on analysis of master's dissertations submitted to the department of sociology and anthropology, University of Maiduguri from the year 2010 to 2019 is intended to bridge some of these gaps.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the study are to determine:

1. The types of information materials cited in masters' dissertations submitted to the Department of Sociology and Anthropology, University of Maiduguri.
2. The most frequently cited materials title in masters' degree dissertations submitted to the Department of Sociology and Anthropology, University of Maiduguri.
3. The currency of materials cited in masters' degree dissertations submitted to the Department of Sociology and Anthropology, University of Maiduguri.

Research Questions

The research questions were posed to guide the study:

1. What are types of information materials cited in masters' degree dissertations submitted to the Department of Sociology and Anthropology, University of Maiduguri?
2. What are the most frequently cited materials titles in masters' degree dissertation submitted to the

Department of Sociology and Anthropology, University of Maiduguri?

3. What is the currency of the materials cited in masters' degree dissertations submitted to the Department of Sociology and Anthropology, University of Maiduguri?

Literature Review

Onwubiko and Ofor (2023) worked on citations of Masters Theses in Library and Information Science of Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka, Nigeria submitted from 2011 to 2018 with a view to determining the format and age of materials used and most frequently cited journals. The document checklists were used for data collections and the citations were extracted from the title pages and reference lists of each of the theses. Data obtained from 48 Masters Theses were examined. The study found that 47.22% of cited items were monographs followed by journals - 31.21%, 8.5% were reports, 4.05% were web resources and 3.65% were conference proceedings. This is contrary with other citation analysis, which found that journals are the most frequently used format. The study also revealed that 21 journal titles were the most frequently cited journals by Library and information Science postgraduate students. The study discovered that the average age of materials used were 10- 20 years and that Library Philosophy Practice (e-journal) was the most cited journal title. The findings did show that citation analysis of theses is veritable tool for collections development. The implication of this study is that it could serve as a collection development tool that can be used as a model for the library to identify the primary sources for acquisitions and also as a guide for collection maintenance. It is based on this that it was recommended that university libraries should as a matter of professional responsibility ensure yearly

analysis of theses as part of their documentation policies.

In a similar study by Gunasekera (2016) found out that Sociology theses contained 1603 citations and average number of citations was 115 with a range from 53 to 233 whereas economics theses contained 1975 citations (Average 110) with a range from 22 to 227 citations. A total of 28 master's theses and 04 doctoral dissertations which produced thirty-two in all were gathered and 3578 citations were generated and the average number of citation was 112 with a range from 22 to 233 citations. The study by Mahajan and Kurnar (2017) revealed that out of 3721 citations cited in the Ph.D. theses submitted in the Department of Sociology, books comprised the highest citations (2145, 57.65%) followed by journals' citations (1359, 36.52%), websites/Internet sources (94, 2.53%), conference proceedings (63, 1.69%) and reports (60, 1.61%). Since books and journals together accounted for 94.17% citations, authorship pattern; half-life, etc. were calculated for such documents only. Another similar study is carried out by Singh & Bebi in 2013 which found out that researchers in the discipline of Sociology cited more books, followed by journals articles.

Methodology

The study employed descriptive research design using bibliometric techniques. Documentary were used as instrument of the study. The population of this study comprised of 67 masters Dissertations submitted to the department of Sociology and Anthropology, University of Maiduguri from the year 2010 to 2019 available at the time of this study. The researcher considers the whole population useful as it was small and manageable. Therefore, a Census Sampling Technique was adopted for the study. The sorted dissertations were analyzed using descriptive statistics of frequency count and percentages.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

The data collected for this study was obtained from the documentary sources (Dissertations) analysed and presented based on the three (3) research questions guided by the study. The response rate indicated that sixty seven (67)

copies of dissertations were expected to be analysed, fifty two (52) dissertations were thoroughly treated which was 78% of the total dissertations expected to be analysed and was considered useful. The non-response rate was 15(22%) which were not treated.

Table 1a: Response Rate for Journals

Number of Dissertation	Total Number of Journals from 52 Dissertations	Number of Core Journals	Frequency of Core Journals	Number of Non-Core Journals	Frequency of Non-Core Journals	Total Frequency of Core & Non-Core Journals
52	577	30	362	547	444	806

Table 1a shows that fifty two (52) numbers of dissertations were used for the study, five hundred and seventy seven (577) total numbers of journals were found from the 52 dissertations, thirty (30) numbers of core journals and five hundred and forty seven (547) sum the total number of journal from 52

dissertations. While, three hundred and sixty two (362) frequency of core journals and four hundred and forty four (444) frequency of non-core journals, which sum the total of frequency of core and non-core journals. The researcher used Journals that appeared more than four (4) times in dissertations and considered it as core journals.

Table 1b: Response Rate for Books

No of Dissertation	Total Number of Books from 52 Dissertations	Number of Books Mostly Used	Frequency of Books Mostly Used	Number of Books Less Used	Frequency of Books Less Used	Total Frequency of Books Mostly Used & Less Used
52	1278	15	149	1263	1141	1290

Table 1b shows that fifty two (52) numbers of dissertations were used for the study, one thousand two hundred and seventy eight (1278) total numbers of books were found from the 52 dissertations, fifty (15) numbers of books mostly used and one thousand two hundred and sixty three (1263) sum the total

number of books from 52 dissertations. While, one hundred and forty nine (149) frequency of books mostly used and one thousand one hundred and forty one (1141) frequency of books less used, which sum the total of frequency of books mostly used and less used.

Research Question 1: What are types of Information Materials Cited in master’s degree dissertations submitted to the Department of Sociology and Anthropology, University of Maiduguri?

Table 2: Types of Information Material Cited

S/N	Types of Material Cited	Frequency	Percentages
1	Books	1278	41%
2	Journals	577	18%
3	Conference Proceedings	330	10.5%
4	Yearbook/Handbook	64	2%
5	Theses/Dissertations	66	2%
6	Government Documents	94	3%
7	Electronic Resources	176	6%
8	Technical Reports	394	12.5%
9	Magazines/Newspapers	148	5%
Total		3127	100%

Table 2 shows that a total of 3127 (three thousand one hundred and twenty seven) sources were cited. It is obvious from the above table that books contribute the highest number of citations with 1278(41%) of the total citations, journals are the second highest with 577(18%) of the total citations. Technical report is the third highest with 394(12.5%) of the total citations. Conference proceedings constitute 330(10.5%), followed by electronic

resources with 176(6%), Magazines/Newspapers constitute 148(5%), Government documents were cited 94(3%), Yearbook/Handbooks constitute 64(2%), while Theses/Dissertations constitute 66(2%) of the total citation. This shows that master’s degree students preferred to use books and journals than other sources of information. This is because they have ease of access and they are available within their reach.

Research Question 2: What are the most frequently cited materials titles in master’s degree dissertations submitted to the Department of Sociology and Anthropology, University of Maiduguri?

Table 3a: Title of Books Frequently Cited

S/N	Title of Books	Frequency	Percentage
1	Population and development review	28	19%
2	Social science and medicine	22	15%
3	Social Forces	19	13%
4	American sociological review	13	9%
5	Economic Development and Cultural Change	8	5%
6	Reading in Applied Psychology	7	5%
7	Women and Education	7	5%
8	World Development	6	4%

9	Work and Occupation	6	4%
10	Child Development	6	4%
11	Family Planning Perspective	6	4%
12	Crime and Delinquency	6	4%
13	Sociological Forum	5	3%
14	Social sciences medicines	5	3%
15	Chin Rehabilitation	5	3%
TOTAL		149	100%

Table 3a shows 15 books frequently cited in master’s degree dissertations submitted to the Department of Sociology and Anthropology, University of Maiduguri within the study period. The researcher used books that appeared more than four (4) times in dissertations and considered it as books frequently cited. A total of 149 books frequently cited were found. Population and development review had highest number with 28(19%), followed by social science and

medicine 22(15%), then social forces 19(13%), American sociological review 13(9%), economic development and cultural change 8(5%), reading in applied psychology 7(5%), women and education 7(5%). World development, work and occupation, child development, family planning perspective and crime and delinquency with 6(4%) respectively. Sociological forum, social sciences medicines and chin rehabilitation with 5(3%) each respectively.

Table 3b: Title of Journals Frequently Cited

S/N	Title of Journal	Frequency	Percentage
1	Journal of abnormal Child Psychology	48	13%
2	Journal of college counselling	35	10%
3	Journal of studies in family planning	31	8%
4	West African Journal of Medicine	25	7%
5	Journal of criminology	20	6%
6	Journal of population studies	18	5%
7	The stroke journal	17	5%
8	Journal of clinical psychology	11	3%
9	International journal of family planning perspective	11	3%
10	Journal of child abuse and neglect	10	3%
11	The demography journal	10	3%
12	Journal of behavioural therapy research	10	3%
13	African journal of Reproductive health	10	3%
14	British Journal of Criminology	9	2%
15	Journal of research in crime and delinquency	8	2%
16	Ilorin journal of Education	7	2%

17	Journal of biosocial science	7	2%
18	Journal of marriage and family	7	2%
19	Journal of health and social behaviour	7	2%
20	Journal of social sciences	7	2%
21	Journal of financial crime	6	2%
22	African Journal of criminology and justice studies	6	2%
23	East African Medical journal	6	2%
24	Journal of social and management studies	6	2%
25	Journal of abnormal and normal social psychology	5	1%
26	Journal of abnormal psychology	5	1%
27	Crime and delinquency	5	1%
28	Sokoto journal of social science	5	1%
29	Tambari journal of Education	5	1%
30	Drug and alcohol dependence	5	1%
TOTAL		362	100%

Table 3b shows 30 core journals most frequently cited in master’s degree dissertations submitted to the Department of Sociology and Anthropology, University of Maiduguri within the study period. The researcher used Journals that appeared more than four (4) times in dissertations and considered it as core journals. A total of 362 journals were found. Journal of abnormal Child Psychology had highest number with 48(13%), followed by Journal of college counselling 35(10%), then Journal of studies in family planning 31(8%), West African journal of medicine 25(7%), Journal of criminology 20(6%), Journal of population studies 18(5%), and the stroke journal 17(5%), journal of clinical psychology and international journal of family planning perspective with 11(3%) respectively and journal of child abuse and neglect, the demography journal, journal of behavioural therapy research, and African journal of Reproductive health with 10 (3%) each, British Journal of Criminology 9(2%), Journal

of research in crime and delinquency 8(2%), Ilorin journal of Education, Journal of biosocial science, Journal of marriage and family, Journal of health and social behaviour and Journal of social sciences with 7(2%) each, Journal of financial crime, African Journal of criminology and justice studies, East African Medical journal, and Journal of social and management studies with 6(2%) respectively, Journal of abnormal and normal social psychology, Journal of abnormal psychology, Crime and delinquency, Sokoto journal of social science, Tambari journal of Education, and Drug and alcohol dependence 5(1%) each respectively.

Research Question 3: What is the currency of the materials cited in master’s degree dissertations submitted to the Department of Sociology and Anthropology, University of Maiduguri?

Currency is determined by calculating the length of time a particular reference material has existed and these can be measured in years. The currency of citation was calculated using the formula. $A = SY - PY$

Where: A = Age of reference material

SY = Submission year of dissertation

PY = published year of cited material

Key: Very current: 1-5years

Fairly current: 6-10years

Not current: 11years and above

No date (nd): Without publication date

Table 4: Currency of Information Materials Cited

S/N	Year of Submission	Very Current	Fairly Current	Not Current	No Date	Total
1	2010	28	51	70	13	162
2	2011	19	37	83	7	146
3	2012	31	30	201	12	274
4	2013	17	36	97	1	151
5	2014	38	37	109	4	188
6	2015	41	47	205	11	304
7	2016	67	55	219	5	346
8	2017	93	101	202	26	422
9	2018	198	139	215	31	583
10	2019	98	189	237	27	551
Total		630(20%)	722 (23%)	1638(52%)	137(4%)	3127

Table 4 shows that, majority of the citations 1638(52%) were 11 years and above considered not current, 722 citation representing (23%) of the total citations between 6-10 years and are considered fairly current, 630 citation representing (20%) of the total citations between 1-5 years and are considered very current, while 137 citations representing (4%) of the total citations have no date of publication. This implies that, majority of the cited materials between 2010-2019 years of submission were not current.

Summary of Findings

Based on the analysis, the findings of the study are presented as follows:

1. The result revealed that, there were nine (9) different materials and majority of the information materials cited were books then followed by journals
2. Majority of the most frequently cited materials titles in master’s degree dissertations was Population and development review for book and Journal of abnormal Child Psychology for Journal
3. The currency of the materials cited in master’s degree dissertations revealed that, majority of the citations were 11 years and above considered not current.

Discussion

The study was based on three (3) research questions addressed in the study. A descriptive research design was adopted using bibliometric techniques. The researcher used observation and documentary as instrument of the study. A total number of fifty two (52) dissertations were identify and analyzed which generated a total number of three thousand one hundred and twety seven (3127) sources were cited. The study found that Master's Degree student under study gave more preference to books and journal articles to other sources of information when conducting their research. This finding corroborates the study of Mahajan and Kumar (2017) who investigated Citation Analysis of Doctoral Theses in the Field of Sociology submitted to Panjab University, Chandigarh (India) during 2002-2012 in order to determine the different types of information material cited, his study found out that books are more cited by Ph.D Student than articles.

The finding on most frequently cited materials revealed that, majority of the most frequently cited materials titles in master's degree dissertations was population and development review for book and Journal of abnormal Child Psychology for Journal. To identify the most frequently cited materials, the title of the books and journals has been arranged in descending order of the number of citations received with their frequency and percentage. Fifteen (15) most frequently cited books and thirty (30) most frequently cited journals were identified using the number of citation received by each books and journals tittle. This finding corroborates with the study by Zafrunnisha (2012), in SRI Venkatewara University Tirupati, India who found out that, the first four (10) books in the frequency list contribute nearly 25% of total books cited, while the first 33 journals in the frequency list contribute nearly 50 % of total journal cited.

The currency of information materials cited by master's degree student under study revealed that, most of the information materials used were 11 years and above considered not current. This finding is in line with the study of Navaneetha (2014) on the currency of publication of material using a Bibliometric analytical method during the period of 1960-2012 derived from Scopus database revealed that, out of 1795 publication published during the period 1960 -2012 only 169 (9.42%) were published in 2010 the analyses revealed that, majority of the sources cited were obsolete. In a similar study by Angamma and Jayatissa (2015) and Gunasekera (2016) in Sri Lanka, the highest citation about 91% of the total citation in the sociology theses were recorded in the period from 1951-2000. The result concluded that most of the citations used by researchers were not current.

Conclusion

The study established that the types of information materials cited were nine (9) from which books and journals had the highest number than other citation. The study concludes that postgraduate students should also make use of other information materials such as conference proceedings and electronic resources so as to enhance the opportunity to cite current information materials. The findings revealed that most frequently cited materials title were population and development review for books and journal of abnormal Child Psychology for journals. These titles could be much more understood when compared with books and journals that cover a wide scope of different fields. The study revealed that population and development review and journal of abnormal Child Psychology were the most used materials may be because of the free accessibility of the materials as it has both soft and hard copies available in the field of sociology and anthropology. The study further indicated that, postgraduate students should be

proactive in searching for information materials so as to avoid citing obsolete resources in their dissertation.

Recommendations

Base on the findings of the study and the conclusion drawn, the following recommendations were made:

1. Postgraduate students should embark on citing more journals than books because of it easy access, free and currency.
2. The acquisitions units of the University library in collaboration with various academic departments should procure more books to ensure efficient and effective resource development so as to provide current and relevant information materials that can enhance service delivery.
3. Postgraduate students should embark on searching for current information materials so as to promote and enhance new knowledge

References

- Angamma, A.M.S & Jayatissa L.A. (2015) A Bibliometrics Study of Postgraduate Theses in Library and Information Science: with Special Reference to University of Kelaniya and University of Kelaniya and University of Colombo, *Sri Lanka Journal of the University Librarians' Association of Sri Lanka* 19 (1)
- Georgas, H., & Cullars, J. (2005). A Citation Study of the Characteristics of the Linguistics literature. *College and Research Libraries*, 66(6), 496-515.
- Gunasekera, C. (2016) Characteristics of Citations in Postgraduate theses of Sociology and Economics: *a Comparative Study; Journal of the University*

Librarians' Association of Sri Lanka 19(2)

- Mahajan, P.& Kumar, A (2017) "Citations Analysis of Doctoral Theses in the Field of Sociology Submitted to Panjab University, Chandigarh (India) During 2002-2012" *Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal)*. 1611. <http://docs.lib.purdue.edu/iatu/2014/bibliometrics/1>

- Navaneetha, K. S. (2014). "Authority Patterns and Degree of Collaboration of Sri Lankan Scientific Publications in Social Sciences and Humanities – a picture from SCOPUS" *library philosophy and practice (e-journal)*. 1153

- Onwubiko, E. C. and Offor, C. C., (2023). "Citation Analysis of Library and Information Science Masters Theses: A Tool for Collection Development in University Libraries". *Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal)*. 7676.

- Onwubiko, E. chidiadi (2023) "Citation Analysis of serials in Postgraduate Theses and Dissertations of Library and Information Science of Public Universities in Southeast, Nigeria" (2023). *Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal)*. 7656. <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/7656>

- University of Maryland (2022). Bibliometrics and Altmetrics: Measuring the Impact of Knowledge. Retrieved from <https://lib.guides.umd.edu/bibliometrics/bibliometrics>

- Zafrunnisha, N. (2012) Citation Analysis of Phd Theses in Psychology of Selected Universities in Andhra Pradesh India" *Library Philosophy and Practice* Retrieved from: <http://unllib.unl.edu/lpp/>